

ANODIC PHENOMENA IN THE ELECTROLYSIS OF LEAD FORMATE

BY A. N. KAPPANNA AND A. S. DEWAGAN

A study of the reactions at gold and platinum anodes in the electrolysis of lead formate solutions has been made. At low current densities up to 15 ma/cm², the only product at the anode is lead peroxide. At higher current densities, the peroxide formation is suppressed to some extent and carbon dioxide liberation also takes place. The presence of free formic acid lowers the current efficiency of the deposition of lead peroxide on the anode. Mechanisms have been suggested to account for the different anodic phenomena.

The earliest work on the electrolysis of aqueous lead formate solutions appears to be that of Warwick (*Chem. News*, 1892, 66, 275). Warwick's idea was to get a cathodic deposit of lead. Electrodeposition of lead from formate solutions was studied more extensively by Mathers and Cockrum (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1914, 26, 117). In neither of these investigations do we have any reference to the anodic reactions in the electrolysis of this salt except where lead anodes were employed. The study of anode reactions in the electrolysis of lead formate is of interest in the light of an observation by Luckow (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1869, 24, 8) that the anodic deposition of lead peroxide from lead nitrate solutions is suppressed by the presence of reducing agents like oxalic acid, tartaric acid etc., and also in the context and continuation of previous studies in this laboratory on the anodic oxidation of formate ion (Kappanna and Deoras, this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 287; 1953, 30, 345). The results of such a study are reported in the present communication.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Lead formate was prepared by the dissolution of lead carbonate in formic acid and crystallised from the solution. Purification of the salt was effected by recrystallisation. A stock solution of the salt was prepared by saturation. The concentration of the solution was determined by the estimation of lead in the solution.

The electrolysis was effected in a 400 c.c. beaker using either platinum or gold electrodes. Potential measurements were all made with a precision potentiometer, and where necessary, a saturated calomel element was used as the reference electrode. Current efficiency measurements were made with the aid of a silver coulometer in the circuit.

TABLE I

Discharge and decomposition potentials.

The lead formate solution used had a concentration corresponding to 0.073 M.

Electrodes.	Anode discharge potential.	Cathode discharge potential.	Decomp. potential.
Platinum	1.33 volts	0.01 volt	1.04 volts
Gold	1.30	0.01	1.31

The anode and cathode current potential curves are quite smooth and normal and do not reveal any abnormalities in the phenomena at the electrodes

Cathodic Reaction.—Deposition of lead commenced almost immediately after the current was switched on even at low current densities, as is to be expected from the low cathode discharge potential. The deposits were in all cases flaky and not adherent. The current efficiency was found to be nearly 100%.

Anodic Reaction: Platinum Electrodes.—The colour of the anodic deposit varied slightly with current density. At low current densities it was reddish brown and deepened towards dark brown with increase in current density. The composition of the deposit was ascertained by analysing it both for its lead content and available oxygen. In all cases the deposit proved to be entirely lead dioxide. The difference in density of colour is obviously due to the difference in grain size.

There was no gas evolution at the anode up to a current density of 15 ma. Above this current density, there was gas evolution as well as deposition of lead dioxide. Anodic gases collected at different current densities proved to consist of CO_2 and small quantities of oxygen.

Gold Electrodes.—The results with gold electrodes were slightly different. Even at low current densities (5 ma) gas evolution was visible, but even so, the deposition of lead dioxide went on smoothly, though not exclusively. These results are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II

Electrolyte.	Area of electrode = $\bar{6}$ cm ² .		
	Current density.	Duration of electrolysis.	Wt. of anodic deposit.
Platinum electrodes.			
(1) 0.073 M lead formate	10 ma	30 mins.	0.132 g.
(2) 0.059 M " "	5	30	0.0596
(3) " " "	5	60	0.119
(4) " " "	10	30	0.120
(5) " " "	10	60	0.238
(6) " " "	15	30	0.182
(7) Do + 0.1 M-Na formate	10	30	0.123
(8) Do + 0.2 M " "	10	30	0.1198
(9) Do + N-formic acid	10	30	0.043
Gold electrodes.			
(10) 0.073 M lead formate	5	60	0.0814 g.
(11) " " "	10	60	0.0832
(12) " " "	15	60	1.048

It will be observed that the amount of deposit on platinum electrodes in the first six results in Table II is very nearly proportional to the amount of current passed (up to a current density of 15 ma) irrespective of the concentration of the lead salt or the presence of neutral sodium formate.

Result (9) in the table is representative of the effect of formic acid in lowering the current efficiency in the deposition of lead dioxide. The result is interesting in so far as it shows that while the presence of formate ion (as by the addition of sodium formate) does not diminish the deposition of the oxide, free formic acid does. This is indicative of the more readily anodic oxidisability of free formic acid (undissociated) than the formate ion through the agency of plumbic ion. It cannot be argued that this is due to the presence of hydrogen ions, as it is well known that the quantitative anodic deposition of lead is effected in the presence of a large excess of free nitric acid. This observation appears to be contrary to the conclusion arrived at by Hammick *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2715; 1926, 1105) that the reactant in the homogeneous oxidation of formate by bromine and iodine is the formate ion and not free formic acid. In the present case, however, we are dealing with a heterogeneous reaction on the surface of an electrode. The reaction probably is

Here again, the anodic gases collected proved to be almost entirely CO_2 (with small amounts of oxygen).

At current densities higher than 15 ma/cm² therefore, the presence of lead in solution exerts a more powerful oxidising influence in the anodic oxidation of formate ion, as there is no liberation of CO at all, as found with only alkali formates. This may mean that the formate radicals liberated on the anode react either (1) according to the equation

or (2) they are oxidised by plumbic ion in accordance with the equation :

Current Efficiency of Lead Dioxide Deposition.—Taking the average of the results of (1) to (8) in Table II, calculations show that 2.17 faradays of electricity are needed for the deposition of one molecule of PbO_2 . This is rough reckoning with millimeter readings. By calculating on the basis of silver deposited in the voltameter included in the circuit, the current efficiency has been found to be in the neighbourhood of 99%.

The current-potential curves have been found to be normal and no breaks occur on the curves right up to very high current densities. This is indicative of the uniformity of the discharge phenomena on the electrodes. The normal primary process on the anode is the discharge of formate ions, yielding formate radicals. The secondary processes following are probably in accordance with the following scheme :

The net electrolytic process could therefore be summed up as :

1. $\text{Pb}^{2+} + 2 \ominus \rightarrow \text{Pb}$ at cathode.
 2. $2\text{HCOO}^- \rightarrow 2\text{HCOO} + 2 \ominus$ at the anode.
 3. $2\text{HCOO} + \text{Pb}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Pb}^{4+} + 2\text{HCOO}^-$
 4. $\text{Pb}^{4+} + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{PbO}_2 + 4\text{H}^+$ } on the anode
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- $$2\text{Pb}^{3+} + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{PbO}_2 + 4\text{H}^+ + \text{Pb}$$

The formation of CO_2 at higher current densities has already been accounted for above. The reason why this should happen above a particular current density is to be understood as due to the increased surface concentration of discharged formate radicals and the possibility of surface catalysis on certain active centres in particular ways. The relative rates of the different surface reactions determine also which should predominate over the rest under different conditions.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
COLLEGE OF SCIENCE, NAGPUR
AND
DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
MAHAKOSHAL MAHAVIDYALAYA,
JADALPUR.

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